

agenda process
green hydrogen

Technical Report

*Findings of the Public Consultation under the Agenda Process for the
European Research and Innovation Initiative on Green Hydrogen*

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1. Introduction

The green hydrogen agenda process is a member state-led research and innovation initiative to build a European hydrogen economy. The process was initiated "bottom-up" at the informal meeting of research ministers on 21 July 2020 and confirmed by the Council Conclusions on the New European Research Area of 27 November 2020. With the help of broad stakeholder participation from science, industry and civil society, the transparent and open process aims to identify the most urgent research issues that need to be addressed to strengthen the competitiveness of green hydrogen in Europe.

The overarching goal is to develop a joint strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA) that covers the entire value chain and offers first action points for implementation. A joint task force of 30 interested member states and third countries steers the process. The agenda process is a complementary initiative to existing activities at EU level and its SRIA developed in close coordination with the European Commission. The agenda process is intended to comprehensively discuss the pan-European interests so that, in a next step, cooperation measures of the member states can be developed on this basis in order to jointly overcome the central challenges of a European hydrogen economy.

Under the German EU Council Presidency, a preparatory workshop was held on 4 December 2020 to achieve a common understanding of the agenda process on green hydrogen. A broad consensus emerged that not only technical issues but also economic, ecological and social aspects such as technology acceptance should be considered along the entire value chain. As a result, three central thematic blocks were defined: 1) production, 2) transport/infrastructure and 3) market stimulation. Cross-cutting issues such as regulations and standards are to be dealt with in all thematic blocks. For each thematic block, a separate sub-agenda process was organised by a member state (or a team of member states): Bulgaria/Italy (production), Germany (transport/infrastructure) and Austria (market stimulation). Each topic was handled by a selected group of renowned experts in the field of hydrogen. So-called 'seed papers' served as a starting point for an online consultation allowing the

general public to discuss and comment on the identified research needs. The comments received were reviewed by the respective expert group and presented in three thematic workshops in autumn 2021.

In this way, many different stakeholders from different countries were directly involved in decision-making processes on green hydrogen. Finally, the results from the individual sub-agenda processes were bundled into a joint strategic research and innovation agenda and will be presented at the final conference in May 2022. The entire agenda process including all milestones is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Timeline and milestones of the agenda process green hydrogen.

2. Methodology

This technical report summarises the results of the pan-European public consultation conducted from 20 August to 1 October 2021. The voluntary consultation was conducted online and open to all people older than 16 years of age. Questions of the consultation were derived from the three 'seed papers' which had been prepared beforehand by the respective expert group. The consultation contained only two mandatory fields (name of country, stakeholder groups), on the one hand to increase participation by allowing for anonymous responses and on the other hand to be able to run group-specific statistical analyses to identify differences between groups.

After the consultation had started, participants were asked to select the 'seed paper' on which they would like to comment. Participants could comment on all 'seed papers' in one go or at different times. Basically, the consultation consisted of two main sections:

- I) Country-specific strategies and conditions
- II) Research questions

The first section primarily contained free-text fields, while the second section was characterised by questions aimed at ranking various research needs according to their relevance on a five-point Likert scale (very high, high, average, low, very low) and to their urgency on a

three-point Likert scale (short, medium, long-term). The temporal dimension was defined differently by the expert groups for production and market stimulation (short <3 years, medium 3-10 years, long-term >10 years) and the expert group for transport/infrastructure (short <5 years, medium 5-15 years, long-term >15 years) due to the different subjects of investigation. Participants were able to add further research aspects previously lacking in the 'seed papers'. The consultation closed with a section where participants could voluntarily provide their contact details in case they were interested to receive further information in the further course of the agenda process.

The full questionnaire is presented in the annex of the technical report.

Sample characterisation

The collected qualitative and quantitative feedback has been examined with respect to additional research aspects and where possible statistically evaluated. Valid responses from about 170 participants were received from 22 countries and all stakeholder groups (science, industry, civil society, public administration). Other groups included cluster and network organisations, associations, public-private partnerships and freelancer. Overall, the participation was balanced across all themes, with around 100 responses, while market stimulation received slightly fewer, around 70 responses.

The response quote was estimated to be ~15%. Most responses were from Germany, Portugal, Italy, Czech Republic, Austria, and Spain (see Figure 2).

In the following sections of the report, the letter n denotes the number of valid responses for a given question and not the sample size.

Limitations

The development of the 'seed papers' including the initial research questions were the responsibility of the corresponding expert group, which led to some differences in the structure and content of the respective questionnaire.

The presented findings partly reflect the opinion of a limited number of participants or even single persons and are therefore not representative for all countries and have to be interpreted with caution. There is a regional bias in the sample, as a disproportionate number of responses came from Germany. However, this only concerns the quantitative analyses; the qualitative data

were evaluated on a country-specific basis. Another possible bias that cannot be conclusively assessed concerns the reliability of the industry's opinion. The authors of this technical report are aware that statements may be mixed with facts and wishes in order not to lag behind the ambitions of other countries or companies.

A fundamental difficulty that some participants had was the understanding of the underlying survey concept. The participants should only evaluate the research questions for themselves, but not yet provide concrete answers. This approach was for some participants too abstract and caused follow-up questions, which were clarified by email or telephone by the secretariat.

For the reasons mentioned above, the results presented in the following will not be interpreted and discussed in depth in this technical report, but rather serve as a data basis for further analyses.

Online consultation (20 Aug - 1 Oct 2021)

- Final status: **1,158 started the consultation, 170 valid surveys** (multiple seed papers in one response possible)
- Response quote: **~15%**
- **22 Countries**
- **TOP5:** DEU, PRT, ITA, CZR, AUT, ESP
- Other: cluster, networks, associations, PPP, freelancer
- **Mandatory fields:** country, stakeholder group

	Production	Transport / Infrastructure	Market stimulation
Industry	31	35	29
Science	33	22	15
Civil society	5	6	7
Public administration	15	13	9
Other	10	10	6
-	5	9	4
Total	99	95	70

Figure 2: Participation in the public consultation in numbers.

3. Research demand

3.1 Production

Q 2. How would you describe the country-specific conditions for the production of green hydrogen?

Q 2a. Are there any national plans to develop a green hydrogen production? Which strategy is followed by your country?

Plans to develop a green hydrogen production

■ under development ■ yes ■ no

Figure 2. Production 2a.1 - Number of countries that have plans to develop a green hydrogen production, n = 89

Colours of hydrogen

■ Blue Hydrogen ■ Green Hydrogen ■ Orange Hydrogen ■ Turquoise Hydrogen

Figure 3. Production 2a.2 - Number of countries that plan to produce different types of hydrogen, n = 89

Q 2b. How far developed are the current hydrogen production facilities? What are the main actors in the field?

Table 1. Production 2b - Stage of development and actors per country as stated by respondents, n = 83

Country	Stage of development as described in the answers	Names of Actors	Actor Groups
Austria	n.a.	Verbund, Voest, Siemens, OMV, Borealis	gas companies gas and energy companies power companies industry petrochemical facilities industrial districts research institutions university oil refineries oil companies power stations utility companies steel industry maritime industry fertilizer industry energy groups industrial groups infrastructure funds solar developers consultants/advisors electrolysis OEMs engineering and EPC providers electrolyser manufacturers infrastructure funds consultants/advisors
Belgium	n.a.	Colruyt, Engie, Fluxys	
Bulgaria	no current facilities for green H2	n.a.	
Cyprus	Does not exist	n.a.	
Czech Republic	grey hydrogen used in petrochemistry and ammonia, 100 ktons of grey hydrogen produced per year, there is a number of plans regarding production of green hydrogen on a smaller scale, but the construction has not started yet	BC-MCHZ, DEZA, ÚJV Řež	
Estonia	Hydrogen is not currently produced at large scale in Estonia	-	
Finland	n.a.	Woikoski Ltd gas company	
France	grey hydrogen (SMR) produced at 800k tons/year	ENGIE, EDF, Air Liquide, H2V, Lhyfe, Compagnie nationale du Rhône, Enertrag, Gazel Energy, Total Energies,	
Germany	only few, preliminary plants first large scale plants are being built SMR (grey) at large scale, PEM/AEW electrolyzers at small scale demonstration/prototype projects in operation for large scale application and significant impact still further steps required pilot projects for several years in particular for power to gas with a focus on the integration of volatile renewable energies pilot projects with potential for scale-up pilot projects with potential for scaling-up Germany is the world-leading country for the production of technology, machines and components for hydrogen production	ENERTRAG, RWE, Siemens, OGE, Air Liquide, Thyssengas, Nowega, Salzgitter, Linde, Thyssen, Sunfire, MCPHY, City of Hamburg, HySON Institut, HH2E, Graforce, Enapter AG, H2Mobility, Shell, Total, Audi, Nel, Raffinerie Heide, Oxfam	
Greece	current production of grey hydrogen by HELPE and MOTOR OIL	n.a.	
Israel	not well developed, pilot stage	n.a.	
Italy	not really well developed	SNAM, ENEL, Terna	
Netherlands	few demonstration projects for green hydrogen, larger plants in study phase	n.a.	
Norway	n.a.	Nel, HydrogenPro, Statkraft, GreenH, Norwegian Hydrogen, Gen2Energy, Equinor, Westgass, Yara, Hydro, Aker Solutions, ZEG-Power	

Portugal	initial stage early stages Current hydrogen production is based on steam reforming, and that H2 just addresses non-energetic markets.	Fusion Fuel, Ultimate Powe, EDP, Galp, REN, DouroGás, Fu- sion Fuel	
Romania	n.a.	Lukoil, Petrotel Ploiesti, Petromidia Navodari, Saint Go- bain Clarasi, Air Liquide, Oltchim, Chimcomplex, Bor- zesti, ICSI Rm. Valcea, UPB, COMOTI, ITIM Cluj Napoca, Petrom, OMV, Brazi	
Spain	several projects under development	Enagás	
Switzerland	could be more developed	SOLIDpower	
United Kingdom	there is currently only a very small amount of electrolytic, hydrogen production, only small scale clean hydrogen production in place at present, larger MW scale projects in planning and GW scale projects expected.	Equinor, BP, Shell, ITM Power, ScottishPower, Pale Blue Dot, Aberdeen City Council, Euro- pean Marine	

Q 2c. Are there any national flagship projects or initiatives promoting the production of green hydrogen?

Table 2. Production 2c - Flagship projects and projects names per country as stated by respondents, n = 84

Country	Flagship projects	Project Names
Austria	Yes	H2Future, Mellach, C2Pat (Carbon2product Austria), Green Hydrogen @ Blue Danube (IPCEI)
Belgium	Yes	Flemish Moonshot Programme
Bulgaria	Yes	n.a.
Cyprus	No	n.a.
Czech	No	Hydrogen Eagle, Black Horse
Estonia	Yes	City of Paldiski, City of Keila
Finland	n.a.	Electrolyser in Kokola, Power 2X Solutions (Harjavalta)
France	Yes	Masshyla, H2V, Horizeo Project
Germany	Yes	GET-H2, Get H2 Nukleus, REFHYNE, Westküste100, Green Motion Steel, Trailblazer, AquaVentus, H2 global platform, Doing Hydrogen (ENERTRAG), Real-labore der Energiewende, IPCEI-projects (62 nominated), Kopernicus projects, H2Mare, TransHyDE H2Giga Hyland projects, Energiepark Mainz, P2X, ENSURE, SynErgie, Hy-Starter, HyExpert, HyPerformeridkraftwerk Enertrag AG
Greece	Yes	SUNIES
Hungary	Yes	Aquamarine
Israel	No	n.a.
Italy	Yes	Hydrogen Valley Puglia
Netherlands	Yes	Green hydrogen and green chemistry programme
Norway	Yes	Northern Lights, 5 IPCEI projects, Nel hydrogen in Heroya, Longship CCS, Celsa Nordix and Statkraft 50 MW electrolyser at Mo Industrial Park, Titanium production at city of Tyssedal with Statkraft
Poland	Yes	Hydrogen Eagle

Portugal	Yes	Bondalti, H2Sines, POSEUR, PRR
Romania	No	n.a.
Spain	Yes	Mallorca harbor, Puertollano (Ciudad Real, Castile-La Mancha), Mallorca Green Hysland, Bilbao, projects led by Iberdrola and Cummins
Switzerland	No	n.a.
United Kingdom	Yes	Gigastack project, Whitelee wind farm, Dolphyn, Oyster, H100 Fife, BIG HIT project

Q 3. One of the goals of the agenda process is to identify research and deployment activities for a better co-operation and networking in hydrogen production at European scale. Further integration of different teams from different countries will foster the H2ERA. The following questions should lead to new insights in this respect.

Q 3a. What are your current activities/interests in hydrogen and hydrogen production?

In the following, the activities that are mentioned are listed and grouped by thematic area (n = 86):

- Green hydrogen production (11 times)
- Commercial scale electrolysis, scale up of hydrogen production, large-scale electrolysis (11 times)
- Solar hydrogen production (technology development, application projects, different technologies) (4 times)
- Fuel cell development (4 times)
- Activities in the full hydrogen value chain (4 times)
- Standardisation and certification (3 times)
- Manufacturing of electrolysers (3 times)
- Hydrogen applied in the mobility sector (2 times)
- Environmental assessment (2 times)
- Pyrolysis (2 times)
- Hydrogen from nuclear energy (2 times)
- Offshore hydrogen production (2 times)
- Application of hydrogen in the industry as feedstock (2 times)
- Education (2 times)
- Grey hydrogen production (2 times)
- Other: electrolysis by-products, hydrogen import, electricity from hydrogen, safety, policy, biomass

Q 3b. What are your plans for hydrogen production in the near and mid-term future in the areas of research, demo and market deployment?

Table 3. Production 3b - Plans in research, demonstration and market deployment, n = 79

Research	Demo	Market deployment
<p>Electrolysis/Fuel Cells:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high pressure electrolysis - PEM electrolysis, - SOEC and SOFC with CSP - ALK electrolysis (cells and stacks) - Capacity increase - Proton-conducting solid oxide cells 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - solar hydrogen production on rooftops - prototypes of solar hydrogen production - large-scale demonstration of 100 MW AEL - scale-up of SOEC - AEL with improved performance and reduced costs - AEM technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PEM electrolysis - scale - up of electrolysis (100 - 400 MW/a) - increase electrolyser manufacturing to 1 GW p.a. - electrolyser core component production
<p>Cross Cutting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cyber security - Standardisation - Efficiency increases - mapping 	local hydrogen valley with PV, biomass gasification, battery stacks and alkaline electrolyser	create a network with customers, co-operation with local energy supplier
<p>Other technologies for hydrogen production:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hydrogen from biomass, waste, biofuels - photocatalysis 	agrivoltaics/marginal lands	hydrogen from biomass and municipal waste
multi-Kw PV-H2 systems	power to liquid plant for sustainable aviation fuels	CCS
metal hydride compressors	local hydrogen production	install power supply equipment
material development		hydrogen for heavy vehicles
hydrogen-based heat		distribution and storage of hydrogen for green public transport and green heat
decentral ammonia production	offshore hydrogen production	large offshore hydrogen production
island solutions		national standard for hydrogen refueling stations
efficiency improvements		
technologies for more efficient separation of hydrogen and natural gas, separation membranes, hydrogen blending		
recycling technologies (electrolysers, fuel cells)		
storage of hydrogen in salt caverns		

Q 3c. What would you consider a priority for hydrogen production in the areas of research, demonstration and market deployment?

In the following, the priorities that are mentioned are listed and grouped by thematic area (n = 85):

- Reduce (investment) costs (18 times)
- Market deployment, market integration (16 times)
- Electrolyser efficiency improvements (9 times)
- SOEC and AEM electrolysis (8 times)
- Expand renewable energy production (8 times)
- Increase the lifetime, durability and reliability of existing technologies (7 times)
- Improve PEM electrolysis (decrease precious metal use) (7 times)
- Funding and incentives (6 times)
- Photo-electrolysis (4 times)
- Standardisation (3 times)
- Plasma pyrolysis technology (2 times)
- High-pressure electrolysis (2 times)
- Offshore hydrogen production (2 times)
- Foster the understanding of policy impacts and impacts of social acceptance (2 times)
- Reversible systems (electrolysis and electricity generation) (2 times)
- Other: real-life demonstration, use of heat and oxygen from electrolysis, comprehensive methodology for island solutions, use of local existing energy sources and networks, cyber security, recycling, cradle to cradle, certification, hydrogen gas turbines, technology openness

Q 4. The agenda process is a bottom-up initiative driven by EU member states and third countries. Please evaluate the following objectives of the initiative in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).

1. Integrating the hydrogen production in the energy system, thus ensuring effective sector coupling, taking advantage of hydrogen being an energy vector
2. Promoting early stage research to force breakthroughs for overcoming scientific and technological challenges in hydrogen production for the different technologies
3. Fostering collaboration between research and industry applying both breakthrough and underpinning approaches at low and high TRLs
4. Fostering company- and technology competition in order to decrease costs of electrolysis (€ net per kW) due to increased performance
5. Fostering company- and technology competition in order to decrease costs of electrolysis (€ net per kW) due to generated scale effects
6. Creation of Hydrogen Business Cases: OPEX based and CAPEX funded business cases
7. Creation of Hydrogen Business Cases: Direct use of electricity for electrolysis and long-term projects with low electricity prices
8. Creation of Hydrogen Business Cases: Additional electrolysis exemption from net fees (grid cost)
9. Increasing resilience of energy system by creating decentralized Green Hydrogen Economies based on Hydrogen Hubs with 10 to 15 MW (and more)
10. Increasing the hydrogen role in a circular economy context
11. Deployment of legislation issues (including regulations, codes and standards - RCS) unified on EU level

Figure 4. Production 4 – Answers grouped by relevance and urgency, n = 86-96

Figure 5. Production 4 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n = 86-96

Q 5. Please evaluate the following research needs in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term)

1. More fundamental research is required, e.g. research needs at low TRLs to address the present gaps. These regard new technologies based on the use of non-critical raw materials characterised by high performance, efficiency and durability.
2. Demonstration activities to favour the rapid creation of a distributed green hydrogen infrastructure in Europe
3. Addressing effective exploitation of results from research projects
4. Companies demands (bridging industry with science); fostering technology transfer
5. Business cases driven R&D (OPEX based Business Cases; CAPEX will decrease later due to company- and technology competition with scale effects and increased performance
6. Joint research and industrial efforts on technological development of recycling of materials and components
7. Addressing a common Terminology at EU level (e.g. JRC Report ‘EU harmonised terminology for hydrogen generated by electrolysis’ published - Ares(2021)4778451)
8. Addressing a common certification of origin to guarantee sourcing of hydrogen from green sources
9. Promoting programmes addressing traceability, deployment mechanisms and market diffusion for green hydrogen production
10. Joint efforts of science, industry and active society for wide public information about the importance of hydrogen production from renewables and its utilization for fast and efficient global decarbonisation
11. Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)

Figure 6. Production 5 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 85-95

	Relevance					Urgency			
	very low	low	average	high	very high	short	medium	long	
1	4	1	16	26	44	48	33	6	
2	6	1	10	29	48	50	34	4	
3	3	3	13	34	38	57	24	5	
4	3	0	19	26	46	48	35	4	
5	4	2	9	39	37	45	34	6	
6	3	1	15	33	41	35	43	8	
7	3	2	14	30	45	65	21	3	
8	4	2	5	17	67	64	21	6	
9	5	2	8	36	40	43	33	10	
10	4	5	12	30	41	54	28	4	
Other	2	0	1	2	10	7	3	1	

Figure 7. Production 5 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n = 85-95

Q 6. What is your opinion on the establishment of a common digital platform for the exchange of information?

Figure 8. Production 6 - Opinion on a common digital platform (number of answers), n = 70

Q 7. Fast deployment of clean hydrogen solutions faces not only research and technological challenges. A successful transition towards a European hydrogen economy requires a unified, stable and friendly legal framework at EU level as well as societal acceptance.

Q 7a. What do you think society wants to know about hydrogen production?

In the following, the answers are listed and grouped by thematic area (n = 80):

- Safety (41 times)
- Environmental impact, sustainability, land and water use (33 times)
- Costs of hydrogen scale-up, price of hydrogen, cost of the transition, affordability, impact on other fuel costs (29 times)
- Explanation of the impact of hydrogen technologies along the whole value chain (10 times)
- Security of supply, availability (10 times)
- Independent information (8 times)

- Job opportunities (6 times)
- Social fairness (5 times)
- Possibilities of hydrogen use (4 times)
- Why hydrogen is indispensable or necessary (2 times)
- Life cycle analysis (2 times)
- Other: Facilitate hydrogen vehicle use, technological leadership

Q 7b. What shortcomings in the current policy do you see to raise public awareness about hydrogen production?

Respondents mentioned the shortcomings in the current policy and also proposed action points. For this evaluation, these have been paraphrased, grouped and summed up (n=70).

Shortcomings listed by the respondents:

- Lack of a Science-backed multilateral vision and a clear roadmap
- Politics are too passive, unclear signalling, lack of focus, weak policy support
- Low level of knowledge on behalf of policy makers, administration, institutions, private sector
- The current framework leaves too many open questions on price and affordability
- Lack of specific information and public awareness
- Bureaucracy
- Lobbyism
- Public expectations on the hydrogen economy are too high
- Too much focus on blue hydrogen
- Lack of trust in politics and big corporations
- Energy transition is too slow
- Lack of standards and certification

Action Points proposed by the respondents:

- Built up public transportation using hydrogen
- Highlight that for a rapid GHG reduction existing technologies have to be used, hydrogen is a future technology
- Stress that hydrogen is a co-technology to batteries and other solutions
- Stress the multimodality of hydrogen application
- Communicate that hydrogen is safe
- Politicians should focus on the direct use of electricity in heating and mobility sector
- Communicate that hydrogen is the second pillar of decarbonisation
- Education
- Technology openness
- Communicate the difference between blue and green hydrogen in terms of climate impact
- Use of social media and communication technologies
- Realism about the TLR of hydrogen technologies
- Accept hydrogen imports to the EU
- Continue with the thorough participatory process that involves relevant stakeholders and members of the civil society
- Demonstrate the economic and social benefits of the hydrogen economy
- NGOs and scientific community can give credibility
- Dissemination activities on risk assessment, environmental and social performance of hydrogen technologies
- Stop fossil fuel subsidies

Q 7c. What measures would you suggest to improve the acceptance of hydrogen?

In the following, the answers are listed and grouped by thematic area (n = 75):

- Demonstration projects (21 times)
- Awareness campaigns, public campaigns, information (18 times)
- Discuss safety honestly (9 times)
- School and university education (8 times)
- Focus on sustainability, climate change aspects (5 times)
- Hydrogen use in public activities (e.g. public transport)
- Transparency, open communication (4 times)
- Other: Focus on acceptance issues around renewable energies, compile and communicate a roadmap, measure and communicate the price of non-renewable fuels

Q 8. Please evaluate the following arguments in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).

1. Green Hydrogen production will strengthen the European energy security
2. Green Hydrogen production could become cost competitive with natural gas at a CO2 price of 80 €/t
3. Green Hydrogen production could become cost competitive with natural gas at a CO2 price of 150 €/t
4. We need a strong public educational campaign introducing people to the nature, qualities and use of Green Hydrogen
5. We need a clear assessment of the impact of Green Hydrogen production on water resources
6. We need further studies on the safety of Green Hydrogen production
7. Society in my country is generally concerned about the safety of using H2

Figure 9. Production 8 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 74-95

	Relevance					Urgency			
	very low	low	average	high	very high	short	medium	long	
1	5	1	14	21	51	23	35	28	
2	10	11	18	23	20	16	31	27	
3	9	6	17	28	22	21	33	22	
4	8	7	9	28	42	55	27	5	
5	10	13	11	29	32	50	24	12	
6	7	10	18	28	32	55	24	8	
7	15	16	26	22	16	46	26	8	
Other	1	0	0	0	8	3	1	2	

Figure 10. Production 8 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n = 74-95

Q 9. Further comments

In the following, a selection of further comments given by the respondents is summed up and paraphrased (n = 23):

- Include financing aspects in the research objectives and the position paper
- Include other forms of clean hydrogen, not only green hydrogen
- Respondent argues for synthetic natural gas and biogas instead of hydrogen as hydrogen is difficult to handle and store
- Highlight the need or an increase in renewable energy plants
- R&D should focus on large-scale electrolysis to decrease costs
- Consider the usage of oxygen, its handling and oxygen infrastructure needs, as it is a by-product of electrolysis
- research must concentrate on countries that can and will generate renewable power in excess of local demand for import
- critically assess the deployment of hydrogen in end-uses, consider other potential contributors to decarbonisation such as electrified road transport, heat pumps etc.
- leverage the potential of AEM electrolysis
- only green hydrogen is clean hydrogen, it is right that the research agenda focuses on green hydrogen
- define the concept of “biomass for energy” in terms of low/high quality to avoid abuse of landfill
- act fast and remove barriers of entry
- need for a European general framework

3.2 Transport and Infrastructure

Q 2. How would you describe the country-specific conditions for the transport of green hydrogen?

Q 2a. & 2b. Are there any national plans on the development of transport infrastructure for green hydrogen?

Which strategy is followed by your country?

Table 4. Transport 2a & 2b - Countries' strategy regarding transport and infrastructure, n = 72

Country	National plans on transport infrastructure	Further comment and country's strategy
Austria	No	n.a.
Bulgaria	No/unsure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Newly built hydrogen pipelines - Hydrogen blending - Hydrogen roadmap is being prepared - Export-focused strategy
Cyprus	No	
Czech Republic	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Repurposing natural gas networks - European hydrogen backbone - Truck transport of hydrogen - Mainly import-focused
Estonia	No	n.a.
France	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - French hydrogen strategy does not target transport infrastructure - Strongly decentralized hydrogen
Germany	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gas infrastructure regulation - Hydrogen blending into the gas networks - Newly built hydrogen pipelines - Storage in salt caverns - Newly built offshore pipelines - Transport by trucks - Strongly import-focused strategy (as LOHC, ammonia or liquid hydrogen, via pipelines and ships) - Repurposing of natural gas networks - Respondents paint a mixed picture on whether the strategy is centralized or decentralized
Greece	No	n.a.
Italy	Yes/unsure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hydrogen shipping (LOHC) - Hydrogen blending up to 10% - 70% of Italian gas networks are ready for 100% hydrogen - Import from North Africa - Respondents paint a mixed picture on whether the strategy is centralized or decentralized
Latvia	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ministry of Economics proposed hydrogen blending up to 2% - 60% of hydrogen demand inland production, 30% import
Netherlands	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Repurposing natural gas networks - Newly built (open-access) hydrogen backbones - Several regional initiatives in industry clusters that will eventually link to the backbone - Import-focused strategy, especially ship imports through national harbours; export of imported hydrogen to Germany
Norway	No	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hydrogen shipping in focus (liquid hydrogen) - Truck transport of compressed hydrogen - Export of liquid hydrogen and ammonia by ship
Poland	Unsure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Repurposing and newly built pipelines

		- Decentralized strategy
Portugal	Unsure	- Willingness to connect to European hydrogen backbone - Necessity for storage and distribution infrastructure is acknowledged, respondents are conflicted on the existence of plans - Import of liquid hydrogen via ships - Decentralized strategy
Romania	No	- Repurposing of natural gas pipelines seen as the first step
Slovenia	No	- Scattered initiatives
Spain	Yes	- Repurposing natural gas pipelines - Newly built hydrogen pipelines - Truck transport - 100-150 hydrogen refueling stations targeted - Strongly export-focused strategy
United Kingdom	Yes	- Repurposing natural gas pipelines - Scotland is seeking to export hydrogen (via pipeline or ship)

Q 2c. Is your national infrastructure ready to absorb adequate amounts of hydrogen?

Table 5. Transport 2c - Hydrogen readiness of infrastructure components, n = 64

Infrastructure components or aspects that are already hydrogen-ready	Number of countries for which respondents reported this aspect	Infrastructure components that require more effort or aspects that make the transition more difficult	Number of countries for which respondents reported this aspect
Repurposing of the gas infrastructure	4	New hydrogen pipelines	2
Adaption of technical standards	2	Low TRL	1
Blended hydrogen up to 2%	2	Lack of transport infrastructure	2
Blended hydrogen up to 5%	2	Low hydrogen demand/supply	2
Blended hydrogen up to 10%	3	Lack of customer connection to main network	1
Blended hydrogen up to 20-22%	3	Conversion of industrial technologies to hydrogen resistant	1
Small adaptations of distribution gas network	1	Storage	1
Refueling stations built	1	Time constraint	1
Usage of stranded gas infrastructure	1		
R&D pipeline infrastructure (materials resistance, hydrogen compressors)	1		

Q 2d. What are the main actors in the field?

Table 6. Transport 2d - Main actors, n = 67

Country	Name of entity as stated by respondents
Czech Republic	APT, spol. s r. o., Unipetrol, Spolchemie, Net4Gas, Pražská plynárenská, ČEZ a.s., ČPS (Český plynárenský svaz), Orlen Unipetrol, Asociace plynovodů a produktovodů z.s. – ASPP, GasNet, Czech Gas Association, Energy Regulatory Office
France	GRTgaz, Terega, GRDF

Germany	Enertrag, Linde, CEMEX, Sunfire, Gascade, ONTRAS, Zweckverband IPSP, Energiequelle, 50Herz, Kreiswerke Barnim GmbH, Hydrogen Europe, H2.B, EEHH, H2-Mobilty, Air Liquide, DWV, DVGW, VDMA, MWV, RWE, OGE, Gasunie, Gascade, Thyssengas; National Organisation Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Technology (NOW GmbH), Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy, Federal Network Agency for Electricity, Gas, Telecommunica, GASAG; Stadt Hamburg, Stadt Sonneberg, Siemens Energy, Raffinerie Heide
Italy	SNAM, ENI
Latvia	Conexus
Netherlands	Gasunie
Norway	Statkraft, Everfuel, Hynion, Hydro, Equinor, BKK, Yara
Portugal	Galp Gás Natural Distribuição (GGND), Ren Portgás, Sonorgá, Ren Gasodutos, EDP, Bondalti
Romania	National Research and Development Institute for Cryogenics and Isotopic Technologies ICSI Râmnicu Vâlcea, COMOTI, University Politehnica of Bucharest, National Research and Development Institute for Isotopic and Molecular Technologies Cluj-Napoca, "Gheorghe Asachi" Technical University of Iași Lukoil, Petrotel Ploiesti, Petromidia Navodari, Saint Gobain Calarasi , Air Liquide, Oltchim, Chimcomplex Borzesti, Petrom, OMV, Brazi
Spain	Enagás, Redexis, Nortegas, Tecnalía, Spanish Hydrogen Association, SEDIGAS
United Kingdom	ERM, SGN, Peterhead Port, ETZ, Port of Cromarty Firth, National Grid, Ineos, Forth Ports, Cadent, NGN

Q 2e. Are there any national flagship projects or initiatives promoting the transport of green hydrogen?

Table 7. Transport 2d - Flagship projects, n = 65

Country	Projects names
Bulgaria	National recovery and resilience plan
Cyprus	2-3 demonstration projects (unnamed)
Czech Republic	European hydrogen backbone, Hydrogen Eagle (Orlen Unipetrol), Black Horse
France	The Mosahyc Project, Lacq Hydrogen
Germany	GET-H2, h2vorOrt, AquaDuctus, HyPerLink, Green Octopus, Clean Hydrogen Coastline, GET H2 IPCEI, Doing Hydrogen project and sub-project "Electrolysis Corridor East Germany", European Hydrogen Backbone Initiative, HyLand (BMVI projects), HyperLink, AquaVentus, TransHyDE, Hydrogen Cluster East Brandenburg, Stadt Hamburg, Stadt Sonneberg, Reallabor Westküste 100, GET H2 Nukleus, H2Stahl, Energiepark Bad Lauchstädt
Greece	SUNIES
Italy	H2IT (Italian Association for Hydrogen and Fuel Cells)
Latvia	European backbone initiative
Netherlands	HyTransport, Deltacorridor, Hyway27
Norway	HySHIP-project
Portugal	The IPCEI anchor project of H2Sines and the Port of Rotterdam.
Romania	Green Hydrogen@Blue Danube
Spain	Green Crane, Green Hysland, HyDeal, Win4H2, Think tank of SEDIGAS
United Kingdom	Project Cavendish, H21 projects, Hydeploy, H100

Q 2f. Are there any particularities in your country that need to be taken into account for the transport of green hydrogen?

Table 8. Transport 2f - Country particularities, n = 53

Country	Particularities stated by respondents
Cyprus	Expenses for new hydrogen infrastructure
Czech Republic	No hydrogen shipment, existing natural gas network, public acceptance, readiness of the infrastructure (grade of steel, compressor stations...)
Estonia	for small distances road transport, for long distances pipelines
France	based on 7 geographical industrial clusters, repurposing gas infrastructure
Germany	repurposing gas infrastructure (due to phase-out of L-gas), an integrated grid- and pipeline-plan, the regulatory framework for hydrogen transportation, large storage capacities in salt caverns, hydrogen storage is strictly limited by location (only in Northern Germany), easy access to the end consumers (industries) is crucial, Germany is a transit country and will keep this role in a hydrogen economy
Italy	repurposing gas infrastructure, ship transport, interconnection with North Africa, capillary gas pipeline network
Latvia	natural gas storage can be reassigned for further hydrogen storage
Netherlands	need of NL-DE connection and cooperation, repurposing gas infrastructure, 5 large demand clusters
Norway	no national gas network, hydrogen production throughout the country, long distances between Norway and central Europe make pipelines less likely and hydrogen shipping more likely
Poland	Old natural gas pipelines
Portugal	modern natural gas infrastructure, hydrogen blending, high cost for exporting hydrogen to central Europe
Romania	repurposing gas infrastructure
Spain	repurposing gas infrastructure, hydrogen export to Europe, storage infrastructure
United Kingdom	repurposing gas infrastructure

Q 3 – Q6. Please evaluate the following research questions in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term)

Q3. Research Questions on hydrogen production

1. How much hydrogen can be expected from national and European sources and what fraction has to be imported globally in the time horizons 2030, 2040 and 2050?
2. How should hydrogen be certified for the carbon footprint of its production process?
3. What is the potential for the production of low carbon hydrogen from alternative sources (pyrolysis of natural gas with CCSU, pyrolysis or plasma gasification of waste, nuclear power plants) in Europe?

Figure 11. Transport 3 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 73-78

Q 4. Research questions on infrastructure options

4. Should the integration of Green Hydrogen be based on a European hydrogen backbone infrastructure from the beginning or will national hydrogen infrastructures be sufficient and more adequate for the initial period until 2030? What will be the long-term perspective for a European hydrogen backbone? How could the two systems best complement each other?
5. What will be the role of container-based transport of hydrogen and hydrogen derivatives versus the transport via hydrogen pipelines in a diverse European context in the transition period until 2030 and in the long term?
6. What are the most viable storage options for Green Hydrogen (physical vs. chemical)?

Figure 12. Transport 4 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 71-76

Q 5. Research questions on planning and regulation

7. Should electrolyzers be located close to the centres of renewable energy supply and storage options centrally in the grid or both rather in the vicinity of demand? Do we need a European coordination for the infrastructure planning or an integrated decision process for infrastructural development in order to integrated H2 efficiently (from technological and cost perspective) into the energy system?
8. Should we plan infrastructures for hydrogen and electricity in an integrated framework or independently?
9. How can the decision processes for hydrogen network planning account for the uncertain demand, production sites and import routes, while also accounting for the vital mid- and long-term role for decarbonisation?
10. What are the requirements for institutional changes for regulating infrastructures (institutional resources, new regulatory arrangements)?
11. What are requirements to change the commodity for existing pipelines (e.g. new approval, based on H2 concentration)?
12. How to adapt current long-term contracts for the transmission of natural gas in case of the transformation to hydrogen transmission?
13. How to engage with citizens to have their support for large-scale new H2 infrastructure?

Figure 13. Transport 5 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 71-77

Q 6. Research questions on research, development and transformation needs

14. What is the state of H2-readiness level (i.e. 100% H2-readiness as well as readiness for H2 blending) of established technologies? What is the economic feasibility of hydrogen technologies (e.g. cost of electrolyzers) in the respective countries?
15. What are the main challenges to be addressed by research, development and innovation in the field of safety of hydrogen infrastructures in particular regarding material development and sensor technologies?
16. What are the main challenges to be addressed by research, development and innovation in the field of

Figure 14. Transport 6 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 69-76

transport options based on hydrogen-derivates like ammonia and LOHC?

17. What are the main challenges to be addressed by research, development and innovation in the field of liquid hydrogen transport?

18. How important is the discovery of new pathways for production and use of hydrogen and how relevant is the related fundamental science?

19. How could regulation, standardisation and certification of new infrastructure components and systems enable the diffusion of Green Hydrogen in Europe?

20. What analytical tools and methods are needed to provide decision support for building-up a new hydrogen infrastructure?

Figure 15. Transport 3-6 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n = 69 - 78

Q 7. Would you like to make further comments or recommendations on the seed paper for transport and infrastructure?

In the following, a selection of further comments given by the respondents is summed up and paraphrased (n = 22):

- Critique on the survey design, respondent wanted to answer the questions instead of rating their relevance and urgency
- Metal hydride materials, tanks and compressors for hydrogen refuelling stations
- France hydrogène roadmap for an ambitious hydrogen strategy:
 - o 2030 targets of 6.5 GW electrolysis are "achievable", 60% more ambitious deployment possible
 - o seven major geographical clusters in France that represent 85% of demand identified
 - o infrastructure would first be developed within the clusters
 - o need for accelerated RES build-up
 - o investment of 10 - 13 billion euros needed (60% of which for electrolysis)
- Focus on green synthetic fuels instead of green hydrogen to use existing infrastructure, address the carbon source as a research priority
- Praise for the thematic focus of the consultation
- Hydrogen from nuclear power is less sustainable than green hydrogen and should therefore not be supported

- If cost-effective and efficient gas separation technologies (e.g. membrane technologies) are available, the transport of natural gas, biogas and synthetic gas, blended and transported in one pipeline should be investigated
- Argues for a European approach that supports and enables the member states and harmonized regulations
- Outlines the activities within hydrogen transport in AquaVentus ((open access) pipeline for offshore hydrogen production in the North Sea, cooperation with other European initiatives in Netherlands and Denmark, hydrogen backbone in Germany)
- Permitting process has to be shortened
- Most of the pipes in the German natural gas infrastructure are hydrogen-ready but other components such as compressors are not
- Infrastructure providers need a reliable regulatory framework
- A robust, liquid market for hydrogen is the fundamental prerequisite for economic feasibility
- Critique on the seed paper's focus on specific countries
- Common IT software or tool for the control of the gas network's "new" hydrogen components and for the guarantee of origin
- Focus on complete, cost-efficient hydrogen value chains
- A hydrogen backbone infrastructure should be envisioned for the decade 2030-2040
- Focus on new materials (composite, nano-) in hydrogen applications
- Need for a framework for research-development-demonstration of new technological solutions
- Stresses the role of gas TSOs and their know-how, argues that they should develop into combined methane and hydrogen network operators
- SSO and LSOs should be supported as storage will be important for a European core hydrogen network
- An interconnected hydrogen pipeline network is of the utmost importance for an integrated energy market

3.3 Market Stimulation

Q 2. How would you describe the country- specific market conditions for Green Hydrogen?

Q 2a. Are there any national plans to develop a green hydrogen market? Which strategy is followed by your country?

Table 9. Market 2a - National plans to develop a green hydrogen market and countries' strategies; the authors of the report are aware that respondents did not directly address the question on hydrogen market but answered on the existence of a roadmap or hydrogen strategy, n = 58

Country	National plans on hydrogen market	Announced plans	Country strategy according to respondents
Austria	No	Renewable energy expansion	n.a.
Bulgaria	In preparation	National Hydrogen Roadmap	H2 export
Cyprus	No	n.a.	n.a.
Czech Republic	Yes	National hydrogen strategy	hydrogen consumption/ import, hydrogen transport hubs, hydrogen technology export
Estonia	Yes	National energy and climate plan	hydrogen production hubs
EU	Yes	European hydrogen strategy	Short term: "low carbon" hydrogen long run: green hydrogen
Finland	No	n.a.	n.a.
France	Yes	National Hydrogen strategy	1. industry decarbonisation + electrolysis market scale-up 2. Renewable hydrogen and "low carbon" hydrogen for heavy duty transport 3. Push for R&D, large scale demonstrators and hydrogen use
Germany	Yes	German National Hydrogen (Implementation) Strategy	1. Make own (green hydrogen) + up to 70% imports ("low carbon" hydrogen + green hydrogen); "low carbon" hydrogen as a transition path; high import in the short run for industrial supply
Greece	In preparation	In preparation: National Strategy by Ministry of Environment and Energy	n.a.
Italy	In preparation	In preparation: Guidelines for a national strategy on hydrogen	Short term: "low carbon" hydrogen long run: green hydrogen
Netherlands	Yes	National Wasterstof Programma	n.a.
Norway	Yes	National Hydrogen Strategy, Hydrogen Roadmap	green hydrogen and "low carbon" hydrogen equally
Poland	In preparation	In preparation: Final draft of Polish Hydrogen strategy	n.a.
Portugal	Yes	National Hydrogen Strategy, EN H2	Make own (green hydrogen) + exports (green hydrogen); targets for installed capacities, gas grid, final energy use, etc.
Slovenia	No	n.a.	n.a.

Spain	Yes	National Hydrogen Roadmap	Production targets until 2030: Make own (green hydrogen): installed electrolyser capacity: 0,3-0,6 GW until 2024, 4 GW until 2030; Demand targets until 2030: 1) 25% green hydrogen in industry's hydrogen consumption, 2) 100-150 public HRFS, 150-200 FCEV buses, 5000-7000 FCEV light and heavy goods vehicles, 3) 2 hydrogen-powered trains
Sweden	No	n.a.	n.a.
United Kingdom	Yes	National Hydrogen Strategy	Make own (green hydrogen + "low carbon" hydrogen) + exports (green hydrogen + "low carbon" hydrogen)

Q 2b. Are there any national regulation, funding programmes, instruments or incentives promoting the production, transport or use of green hydrogen?

Table 10. Market 2b - Existing measures and obstacles to promote green hydrogen within countries, n = 54

Country	Majority vote on existence of national measures	Existing measures (according to respondents)	Obstacles (according to respondents)
Austria	Yes	funding programmes for electrolysers and public transport busses, lighthouse programmes ("climate regions"), Mobilität der Zukunft, KLIEN Programme	n.a.
Bulgaria	no	n.a.	still on research and demonstration level
Cyprus	no	n.a.	n.a.
Czech Republic	no		no funding specific to hydrogen, several funding programmes include hydrogen topics
EU	yes	Funding Compass that gives information on (1) EU funding programmes and funds financed by the 2021 -2027 long-term EU budget and NextGenerationEU and (2) National funding programmes and funds available at EU country level.	
Finland	no	n.a.	Waiting for "Fit for 55" implementation first
France	yes	At least two calls for projects have been opened since the end of 2020 and will be opened until 2022, targeting (1) technologic components and demonstrations (with €275M) and (2) hydrogen ecosystems in territories for industry and mobility (with €325M). Support mechanism for the production of renewable and low-carbon hydrogen produced by electrolysis is currently being prepared, first tenders in 2022, with the aim to support the difference between the production costs of renewable and low-carbon hydrogen and fossil-based hydrogen (SMR as BAT, with around 1.5€/kg).	n.a.
Germany	yes	Funding programmes: - projects to develop green hydrogen production will be funded in the transnational funding programme for Important Projects of common European Interest (IPCEI). - The federal ministry of infrastructure launched the "HyLand" scheme, which includes the funding categories „HyStarter“, „HyExperts“ and „HyPerformer“. These are aimed at regions/municipalities at different stages of the market ramp-up. The different substates also have their own smaller funding schemes concerning the market introduction of hydrogen; - Förderrichtlinie by the BMWi (Funding Guideline by the German Federal ministry of economic affairs and climate action) - Hydrogen Strategy Action Plan: investment and innovation offensive together with the relevant partner - Hydrogen Research Network, Energy Transition Real Laboratories and the National Hydrogen, the 7th Energy Research Programme and Fuel Cell Technology Innovation Programme - Proposed funding volume of EUR 7 billion in the GNHS, however we need implementation speed in funding promises converting into the realization of real projects (i.a. 3 IPCEI funding wave). CCfD programme for industry is to be prepared (first tender in early 2022)	- hydrogen as a product is not yet subsidised and is not yet competitive. - no direct support at the moment, but existing barriers are addressed (e.g. EEG surcharge exemption for electrolysis)

		<p>- H2global: support imports from outside EU (EUR 1bn)</p> <p>Regulations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - regulations under development - reduced taxes on green electricity used for electrolyzers - Adoption of the EEG levy exemption for green hydrogen, REDII implementation in the transport sector with a multiplier of 2 for hydrogen and an overall GHG reduction quota increase to ensure that not only e-mobility contributes to meeting the quota, but moreover also the start-up phase hydrogen is supported. Current debate on network fees: GasNEV regulations should be adopted as far as possible and only targeted adjustments should be made (e.g. to take account of federal subsidies). - "fit for 55" package in order to set the right EU wide framework (Revision RED II, green electricity criteria for the production of green hydrogen, gas package) - In Germany, provisions for a "transition regulation" of pure hydrogen networks ("Übergangsregulierung") are laid down in the German Energy Act (EnWG). More detailed provisions are planned to be developed after the adoption of the new European regulatory framework. <p>Incentives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An instrument incentivising the H2 production will address Carbon Contracts for Differences (CCfDs) and will start shortly on a national basis. - Nationales Innovationsprogramm Wasserstoff- und Brennstoffzellentechnologie (NIP) - There is an indirect incentive for the production of green hydrogen: The Renewable Energy Act (EEG) provides that the electricity used for the electrolysis is exempted from the levy paid by customers to finance the renewable electricity production ("EEG-Umlage" = "EEG apportionment"). 	
Greece	no	In Greece, the hydrogen-related legislation not expected until the second half of 2021 or early 2022. The Greek National Energy and Climate Plan published in 2019 ("NECP") sets out the objectives, policies and measures for the achievement of Greece's energy and climate goals by 2030. In this context, new applications and technologies for the generation of power from RES, such as the production of hydrogen, will likely be assessed through pilot projects.	n.a.
Italy	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "There are many initiatives on these topics, but at the moment I can see only many good clusters and not a real and clear national strategic policy on new energy and environment issues" - under implementation a new law integrating the indications of the Directive RED 2, opening for measures at support of green gases and hydrogen 	n.a.
Netherlands	yes	n.a.	n.a.
Norway	yes	Several funding schemes available along TRL range	n.a.
Poland	yes	n.a.	too low according to needs
Portugal	yes	<p>National regulation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is currently being adapted to allow full implementation of the national strategy. - Portugal has already adopted some legislative measures (implementation of a system of guarantees of origin for renewable gases and definition of objectives for the incorporation of renewable gases) and identified interested companies and national investors. Portugal is also preparing some legislative acts to be published in the upcoming months, namely in the context of the implementation of a system of guarantees of origin for renewable gases. <p>Funding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, the environmental fund and the recovery and resilience plan. <p>Incentives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Several auctions for hydrogen production are expected, more specifically, it is foreseen one for the current year that will be based (as announced) on carbon contracts for difference; POSEUR (CAPEX), H2 auctions (OPEX), Plano de Recuperação e Resiliência (PRR) too low according to needs 	n.a.
Slovenia	yes	It is included in Action plans of SRIP Top (FoF) and SRIP KG (Circular Economy); however, it is not mentioned in the National Recovery and Resilience plan and no funds have been allocated to it to date.	n.a.
Spain	yes	The main official documents and programmes are: 1) The (non-binding) Hydrogen Roadmap already published in October 2020 2) Call for proposals under the IPCEI programme 3) EU funds made available through Member States, e.g. Recovery and Resilience Facility included in NextGeneration EU	n.a.
Sweden	no	n.a.	n.a.

United Kingdom	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Scottish Government has a £100m fund and the UK government has a £240m fund both aimed at capital spend. The Scottish Government will shortly publish an action plan detailing how they will implement their hydrogen policy (published December 2020). UK government is to publish more material in early 2020 following the publication of their strategy in August 2021 - Yes – Net Zero Hydrogen Fund (worth up to £240m) and the Business Models (to provide revenue support for production) - public consultation is now underway 	n.a.
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Q 2c. Are the announced measures in your country strong enough to support fast ramp-up of a green hydrogen economy?

Table 11. Market 2c - Comments on the obstacles for green hydrogen ramp-up, n = 49

Country	Further comments by respondents on the obstacles that hinder a green hydrogen ramp-up
Estonia	plans in very early stages
EU	To support a fast ramp-up of a 'Green Hydrogen' economy, Europe should allow the use of hydrogen in all the sectors that can provide a stable demand, including the heating sector. Blue hydrogen should be supported in the short-term to boost quantity before to move to 100% green hydrogen.
Finland	All directed to ramp up technology and investments rather than market
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Several sources indicate that Germany needs a faster market ramp-up than the governments target of 5 GW electrolysis by 2030. Some say that the industry itself is ready for more, but the government doesn't trust them enough with their commitments. - The measures are a good start, but they are not enough because they hardly lead to an increased share of green hydrogen in Germany at present. - the high price for green hydrogen makes it uncompetitive - participation in this consultation process is important - In general, Germany is supporting the ramp-up but the development of renewable energy is too slow. Energy production and infrastructure are supported by policy, the market side is given little consideration so far. However, political uncertainty in particular with respect to a widespread utilization of hydrogen in all applications of the energy sector (i.e., transportation, residential heating) hampers the development as it introduces associated investment risks. - The hydrogen strategy has increasingly come under criticism. Many stakeholders complain that the expansion paths for renewable energies and Germany are set far too low to achieve the proposed production volume of domestic green hydrogen. At the same time, the national market ramp-up for electrolyzers is too slow, and there are legal risks and there is a lack of investment security. The electricity demand analysis is, therefore, to be considered incompatible with the national climate targets. So far, the concrete implementation of the National Hydrogen Strategy is not as well defined as it should be. There are still several unresolved legal issues regarding the exemption of green hydrogen from the EEG levy. In the national hydrogen strategy, the federal government committed itself to green hydrogen but also envisioned blue and turquoise hydrogen. Consideration of these colors is indeed necessary for the rapid ramp-up of a hydrogen economy. But what's missing is the regulatory implementation of these commitments, and thus an essential prerequisite for investment decisions. To ensure that green hydrogen does not remain a resource artificially kept scarce by regulation, policymakers must create a sub-quota for green hydrogen and massively increase expansion targets for electrolyzers. Every euro invested in climate-friendly technologies is properly invested and urgently needed. - Too much money is wasted - No, the below points must be fulfilled for a successful green hydrogen economy in Germany: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Prioritization of integrated projects along the entire value chain o Raising the expansion path for renewable energies and measures to accelerate RE projects, Pragmatic definition of the green electricity criteria for green hydrogen o Early and ambitious expansion of the hydrogen infrastructure o Approve funding applications for the EU Innovation Fund and the IPCEI in a timely manner o Supply and demand need to grow 'hand in hand'. For this reason support mechanisms need to incentivise both producers and off-takers. There are many potential business models: e.g. Introduction of CCfD to compensate for the higher CO2 reduction costs of H2 technologies for industry, ambitious GHG reduction quotas for the transport sector, RfNBO quotas for other sectors.
Greece	Until now, the announced measures in Greece are not strong enough to support fast ramp-up of a "Green Hydrogen" economy. The measures will be defined according to the strategy that is now being formulated by the Ministry of Environment and Energy. It is a time consuming process, the results of which will be applicable in the long run.
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - While there are currently measures that will prove beneficial in speeding up the transition, there is still much to be done and improvements could be put into place to ensure effective and wider investments. - implementation of national strategy is still too dependent on the permitting process which in Portugal is a considerable issue already for renewable energy projects, and will be far greater for hydrogen projects, given the lack of experience and know-how it exists in the country.

Q 2d. What strengths and weaknesses do you see in your country in terms of a “Green Hydrogen” economy?

Table 12. Market 2d - Countries' strengths and weaknesses for a green hydrogen economy, n = 52

Country	Strengths	Weaknesses
Austria	first funding for electrolyzers and H2-busses	no funding for trucks no port high RE costs
Bulgaria	"clean slate" makes best practices possible	no deployment start from zero
Cyprus	high RE potential possibility to replace current oil dependency with hydrogen	
Czech Republic	H2 is more accepted than battery	no sources of green hydrogen exist limited RE potential
Estonia	RE potential high	lack of infrastructure
Finland	n.a.	lack of grand plan moderate financial resources
Germany	existing infrastructure knowledge of and experience with hydrogen technologies strong and willing innovative industry H2 has a good image in society innovative research institutes and technology developers stable electricity grid many established research projects strong gas market ready for the switch to hydrogen wind power potential	RE potential not sufficient for inland demand slow administration and policy processes taxes and levies for RE are too high short-term roadmap is missing high energy prices lobbying by fossil giants regulation allows blue and turquoise hydrogen hydrogen is expensive missing regulatory framework missing strategy for physical hydrogen grid development missing strategy for decentral market evolution
Italy	good competencies and good geographic location high RE potential in the South strong manufacturing industry and EPC company and operators willing to support hydrogen	lack of political commitment lobbying from fossil sector in the energy authority
Netherlands	experience due to large grey hydrogen production	green hydrogen is not competitive with the low cost grey hydrogen produced in the country
Norway	hydrogen demand from maritime sector	strong push for blue hydrogen instead of green
Portugal	high RE potential at low cost relatively recent gas infrastructure strong support from local agencies for hydrogen hydrogen import/export possible through the port of Sines	lack of capital for investments in hydrogen regulatory uncertainty few demand centers for green hydrogen (one refinery, few chemical industries) political instability negative public opinion
Slovenia	strong research landscape engaged early in hydrogen projects early engagement in Green hydrogen initiatives competence for H2-CHP systems in several engineering companies	no declared national plan for hydrogen within national RRP no support for development and innovation projects for H2
Spain	high RE potential geographic location large and well-developed energy infrastructure industrial resources for all parts of the hydrogen value chain	lack of adequate and robust regulatory framework
Sweden	high RE potential	lack of plans and programmes for green H2
UK	natural resources in Scotland well-developed infrastructure (pipelines, ports, industrial facilities) innovation landscape/ RD&I ecosystem skills from oil and gas sector can be transferred to H2 off-shore wind sector	policy vacuum

Q 3. Please evaluate the following categories of measures to promote Green Hydrogen in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term)

1. Green Hydrogen production Stimulation of commercial demand: e.g. fiscal incentives, CO2-price, cross-border CO2-tax, product CO2-footprint, RE quotas, exemption from taxes and levies, emissions reduction targets, CO2 emissions standards for vehicles, RE share in aviation and maritime fuels
2. International agreements and multilateral cooperation: e.g. harmonised standards and trading rules, removing barriers, globally functioning system of assessing the sustainability criteria, hydrogen guarantees of origin (HGOs), multilingual permit procedures
3. Financing: e.g. long-term signals to foster investor confidence, mitigate salient risks, kick-start financing, grants and loans
4. Demonstration, communication, education: e.g. showing the important contribution to the green deal, clarify safety issues, demonstrate feasibility, create (digital) networks of experts, increase employability in the hydrogen sector through educational programmes
5. Regulatory framework: e.g. fasten permit procedures, regulatory framework for hydrogen infrastructure, trainings for relevant regulatory bodies
6. Public support: funding, providing infrastructure, consistent energy policy (focused and predictable), long-term stability, optimized transport solutions, increase GHG-emission visibility through digitalization
System analysis and assessment on a lifecycle perspective: avoid rebound effects and burden shifting, R&I activities should be pre-assessed vs. its potential to deliver net positive impacts in a full life cycle perspective

Figure 16. Market 3 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 62-67

	Relevance				Urgency			
	very low	low	average	high	very high	short	medium	long
1	4		5	13	45	47	15	3
2	4		10	21	31	34	27	4
3	4	1	6	20	36	47	13	4
4	4	8	9	21	25	42	17	5
5	4	1	1	12	47	48	10	4
6	4	2	5	17	37	45	14	3
7	5	1	17	24	18	27	27	8

Figure 17. Market 3 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n=62-67

Q 4. What are the main barriers to overcome on the way to a “Green Hydrogen” economy? Please evaluate them in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term)

1. Price difference to fossil-based energy-carriers
2. Energy losses in the conversion, storage and transport of hydrogen
3. Government “discrimination” of specific technologies
4. Lack of political courage for appropriate framework conditions
5. Poor public information and therefore little public interest
6. Lack/absence of a credible GO (guarantee of origin) scheme
7. Inconsistent or counterproductive funding rules
8. Obstructive regulatory and regional structures
9. Lack of common international trade rules, harmonized regulations and standards
10. Conflict of use with electrical energy

Figure 18. Market 4 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 52-67

	Relevance					Urgency		
	very low	low	average	high	very high	short	medium	long
1	1	0	3	12	51	40	19	4
2	0	3	19	25	16	19	32	8
3	4	7	21	13	15	32	16	6
4	6	3	15	17	18	34	15	5
5	7	13	18	18	4	17	29	6
6	3	5	8	22	27	38	15	5
7	5	4	18	20	13	27	21	5
8	3	4	10	20	21	33	15	4
9	2	7	11	21	24	23	25	7
10	2	13	16	11	22	26	20	10

Figure 19. Market 4 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n = 52-67

Q 5. How can we best create a level-playing field with fossil energy carriers? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term)

1. No public money for fossil fuel applications
2. No public money for fossil-based hydrogen
3. Increasing fossil fuel prices (CO2-pricing,...)
4. Financial support for “Green Hydrogen” and its application
5. Stepwise legislation towards carbon neutrality

Figure 20. Market 5 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 56-64

6. Charging fossil energy carriers total costs (including external effects such as environment, health related) caused by CO₂-emissions of fossil sources
7. Financial support for CAPEX reduction of technology via scaling up and research
8. Financial support for increase of renewable (cheap) green electricity production

Figure 21. Market 5 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n = 56-64

Q 6. How can we best build up an open and rapidly developing “Green Hydrogen” economy? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term)

1. Cooperation beyond borders
2. Fast introduction of legislation towards carbon-neutrality
3. Develop measures to boost renewable energy production capacities
4. Give easier access to research results for citizen and energy communities
5. Create digital networks of European stakeholders for improving knowledge-exchange and cooperation
6. Strategic strengthening of “Green hydrogen” in existing or new hydrogen strategies and policies (national and European)
7. Creation of strategic demonstration projects and flagship initiatives
8. Exchange of best practice examples

Figure 22. Market 6 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 54-64

Figure 23. Market 6 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n = 54-64

Q 7. Is a bottom-up or top-down approach preferable in order to support Green Hydrogen economy best?

Figure 24. Market 7 - Top-down or Bottom-up approach for a green hydrogen economy? (number of answers, n = 68-69)

Q 8. Which are the most important dimensions for system integration?

Figure 25. Market 7 - Most important dimensions for system integration (number of answers, n = 68-69)

Q 9. Which are the main barriers for sector coupling?

Figure 26. Market 9 - Barriers for sector coupling (number of answers, n = 68-69)

Q 10. Should we focus on concentrated or dispersed renewable energy production/hydrogen supply and utilization systems?

Figure 27. Market 10 - Concentrated or dispersed renewable energy production (number of answers, n = 68-69)

Q 11. Should development (and funding) focus on components or system-integration R&D?

Figure 28. Market 11 - System integration vs. components (number of answers, n = 58)

Q 12. How can we display GHG-emissions along the supply chain at best? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term)

1. Mandatory life cycle assessment (LCA) for all products
2. Certificates of origin for “Green Hydrogen”
3. Develop appropriate digital applications
4. Label products with their GHG-emission footprint
5. Label products with their environmental impact
6. Introduce and display carbon-tax

Figure 29. Market 12 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 55-64

	Relevance					Urgency		
	very low	low	average	high	very high	short	medium	long
1	3	1	5	31	19	24	30	4
2	3	3	8	11	39	40	16	4
3	4	2	28	16	8	15	34	6
4	3	2	12	27	16	28	25	4
5	3	3	17	21	15	22	27	7
6	4	4	7	26	18	26	22	8

Figure 30. Market 12 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n = 55-64

Q 13. How can we inform people at best about “Green Hydrogen”? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term)

1. Municipality workshops
2. Develop easy-to-understand content
3. Integrate renewable energies and hydrogen in school education
4. Make potential emissions “visible” via digitalization
5. Use social media to extend research’s range
6. Continuous learning about “Green Hydrogen” in all types of schools
7. Making positive and negative environmental impacts (local resources, pollution) visible
8. Making regional/local development and employment visible

Figure 31. Market 13 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 49-58

Figure 32. Market 13 – Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n = 49-58

Q 14. How can we support citizen participation in “Green Hydrogen” scenarios? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).

1. Mandatory actions forced by legislation (like vehicle exhaust emission legislation)
2. Roadshows
3. Case-study demo approaches
4. Supporting citizen energy communities
5. Supporting the start-up scene and enabling people to build companies
6. Allowing citizen participation in “Green Hydrogen” investments

Figure 33. Market 14 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 47-58

Figure 34. Market 14 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n = 47-58

Q 15. How can we facilitate plant permit procedures internationally better? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term)

1. Offering multilingual permit procedures
2. Deploy a European permit help desk
3. Speed-up the acknowledgment of digital signatures
4. Create a European legal form to support renewable energies and green hydrogen
5. Develop a platform to access needed national documentations in translation
6. Permit procedures are not a special bottleneck

Figure 35. Market 15 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n = 37-55

Figure 36. Market 15 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n = 37-55

Q 16. How can we create internationally acknowledged vocational trainings and academic programmes to build up a hydrogen work force?

Figure 37. Market 16 - Trainings and academic programmes, n = 68-69

Q 17. How can we secure a resilient international hydrogen supply? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term)

1. Develop models and continue to test them on robustness and sensitivity
2. Commitment to long-term hydrogen supply partnerships
3. Foster efficient energy use and renewable energy supply locally to simplify the additionally needed import and distribution
4. Decentralize the gas market to involve local communities better

Figure 38. Market 17 - Answers grouped by urgency and relevance, n =49-60

	Relevance					Urgency			
	very low	low	average	high	very high	short	medium	long	
1	4	4	8	28	13	28	19	4	
2	4	1	9	17	29	27	22	7	
3	3	0	12	14	28	31	17	5	
4	4	5	18	18	9	12	29	8	

Figure 39. Market 17 - Frequency distribution of the response options on the respective Likert scale, n =49-60

Q 18. Would you like to make further comments or recommendations on the seed paper for market stimulation?

In the following, a selection of further comments given by the respondents is summed up and paraphrased (n = 8):

- Use of hydrogen in the air-intake of internal combustion engines with the goal of increasing (engine) efficiency and reducing exhaust gas emissions proposed as one option for an ad-hoc utilization of small amounts of hydrogen in the transition period
- Focus on niche applications of hydrogen such as the usage chemical hydrides as fuel for drones
- EU regulation should give the possibility to the building sector to use renewable and low-carbon gases as heat in building is already "hydrogen ready"
- There should be incentives for consumers to switch to hydrogen-ready heaters
- Establish EU targets for production and distribution of decarbonized and renewable gases so that there is a clear and binding pathway for the decarbonisation of the gas industry
- Doubt about the hydrogen economy, because of low efficiency (stated 80% loss) and high costs
- Elevate CO₂-prices or make fossil fuels more expensive in other ways
- Support the creation of more efficient devices
- Incentives that address both centralized and decentralized projects/value chains are necessary to stimulate a market ramp-up on all levels
- The introduction of tradable guarantees of origin is necessary based on a uniform terminology of the different climate-neutral gases on a life-cycle basis
- Allow hydrogen prosumers: allow automated flexible energy trading and introduce dynamic energy prices instead of tariffs

4. Conclusion

The public consultation is an essential element of the agenda process on green hydrogen as it allowed the participation of a broad group of stakeholders from EU member states and third countries in decision-making processes. In order to make a low-threshold offer for participation in the agenda process, the survey was implemented online. The responses received were carefully collected and reviewed in order to provide a comprehensive picture of the current European situation with regard to hydrogen and to show the various European perspectives on the subject including the different national research needs.

With a total of 22 countries, a high level of participation and good geographical coverage were achieved, equally encompassing western and eastern regions (EU-13), while providing important impulses for shaping and directing future research activities in green hydrogen. It is in the nature of things that this broad and open approach also captured minority opinions that indicate a certain scepticism about the future potential of hydrogen, but which, with a share of 3% in the

survey, only made up a very small proportion. In general, the initial selection of research questions and the overall focus and structuring of the survey was found to be appropriate by many respondents, which speaks for the high quality of the underlying 'seed papers'.

As to the key outcome of the consultation, all the identified research needs are relevant and urgent to succeed in the energy transition and become a leading European hydrogen economy. There is a great need for support and cooperation in all research areas along the entire green hydrogen value chain. It is therefore of high importance to start with the implementation of EU-wide coordinated research activities and the enabling policy support measures now and to create maximum synergies by combining European competences and financial resources. For implementation, however, the different initial situations of the countries must also be considered. Customised measures are needed to allow all countries to benefit from value creation and to enable them to make long-term progress in the development and utilisation of sustainable energy technologies.

Annex 1 – Questionnaire

Dear Hydrogen Community,

Green Hydrogen plays a key role in achieving the Paris climate targets and in accelerating Europe's transition towards a sustainable and innovative economy based on clean energy solutions. There is great demand for more research and innovation regarding hydrogen solutions to accomplish these goals, however. The production, distribution and storage of green hydrogen, as well as its use in industrial processes and other areas of application, must be established and driven forward through innovation.

At the beginning of 2021, the agenda process on Green Hydrogen was launched as a pilot initiative of the new European Research Area in order to define research priorities and joint implementation activities in a transparent and inclusive participatory process. The agenda process, which originates from the joint programme of the EU Council presidency trio of Germany, Portugal and Slovenia (2020-2021), is driven by many Member States of the European Union, third countries and in close coordination with the European Commission. By bringing together science, industry, civil society and public administration, a joint Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) will be developed in a bottom-up process by the end of this year.

As a starting point, three seed papers have been prepared by leading hydrogen experts in expert groups, covering the thematic areas *production, transport/infrastructure* and *market stimulation*. The papers include an initial list of research questions for an accelerated transformation towards Green Hydrogen in Europe. Due to the different research subjects, the seed papers may vary slightly in their structure and explorative approach.

A public consultation is now calling on all interested parties to contribute their ideas and comments to the seed papers. We would be delighted to receive your opinion on any paper of your choice.

Please, consider the following time estimates for completing the survey:

Section A: Declaration of Consent

- A1. As part of the public consultation, you are requested to provide information about your country of origin and the stakeholder group you represent. Participation is voluntary. There will be no disadvantages for you should you wish not to participate.**

Before you proceed to the survey, we want to inform you about what data will be stored for what purpose and how long. We also want to inform you about the relevant legal basis. Please read the full text of our Statement on Data Protection and, provided you have understood it, please confirm your consent. You will then be directed to the public consultation.

Only persons over 16 years of age are permitted to participate in this public consultation.

Respondents can voluntarily enter their contact details (name, organisation, email address) at the end of the survey in the case they want to be available for further enquiries and receive information on the agenda process in the future. The personal data is connected with the answers given in the survey. The data will be stored for a maximum of three years after the survey for the purpose of sharing information and will not be disclosed to third parties.

Please note: You may exercise your right of withdrawal at any time without stating any reasons and revoke your consent with future effect (greenhydrogen@dlr.de). Please note that the anonymous nature of the survey means that collected data cannot be traced to any specific individual. The data you enter when participating in the survey cannot therefore be easily rectified or erased if you withdraw your consent.

I consent to the processing of the data provided by me for participation in the public consultation on the “Agenda Process Green Hydrogen”. I have read and understood the relevant information in the Statement on Data Protection.

Section B: Seed paper selection

- B1. Please select the seed paper you wish to comment on. If you want to comment on multiple papers, you can either do this in one session or start the consultation again at a later time.**

Production

Transport and infrastructure

Market stimulation

C3. 3. One of the goals of the agenda process is to identify research and deployment activities (current, or planned) for a better cooperation and networking in hydrogen production at European scale. Further integration of different teams from different countries will foster the European Research Area for Hydrogen (H2ERA). The following questions should lead to new insights in this respect. You may answer the questions according to your expertise.

What are your current activities/interests in hydrogen and hydrogen production?

What are your plans for hydrogen production in the near and mid-term future in the areas of research, demonstration and market deployment (select the area according according to your expertise)?

What would you consider a priority for hydrogen production in the areas of research, demonstration and market deployment (select the area according to your expertise)?

C4. 4. The agenda process is a bottom-up initiative driven by EU member states and third countries. Please evaluate the following objectives of the initiative in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term). Relevance

	very high	high	average	low	very low
Integrating the hydrogen production in the energy system, thus ensuring effective sector coupling, taking advantage of hydrogen being an energy vector	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Promoting early stage research to force breakthroughs for overcoming scientific and technological challenges in hydrogen production for the different technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fostering collaboration between research and industry applying both breakthrough and underpinning approaches at low and high TRLs	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fostering company- and technology competition in order to decrease costs of electrolysis (€ net per kW) due to increased performance	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fostering company- and technology competition in order to decrease costs of electrolysis (€ net per kW) due to generated scale effects	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Creation of Hydrogen Business Cases: OPEX based and CAPEX funded business cases	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Creation of Hydrogen Business Cases: Direct use of electricity for electrolysis and long term projects with low electricity prices	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Creation of Hydrogen Business Cases: Additional electrolysis exemption from net fees (grid cost)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Increasing resilience of energy system by creating decentralized Green Hydrogen Economies based on Hydrogen Hubs with 10 to 15 MW (and more)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Increasing the hydrogen role in a circular economy context	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Deployment of legislation issues (including regulations, codes and standards - RCS) unified on EU level	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

C5. 4. The agenda process is a bottom-up initiative driven by EU member states and third countries. Please evaluate the following objectives of the initiative in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term). Urgency

	(<3 years)short-term	(3-10 years)medium-term	(>10 years)long-term
Integrating the hydrogen production in the energy system, thus ensuring effective sector coupling, taking advantage of hydrogen being an energy vector	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Promoting early stage research to force breakthroughs for overcoming scientific and technological challenges in hydrogen production for the different technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fostering collaboration between research and industry applying both breakthrough and underpinning approaches at low and high TRLs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fostering company- and technology competition in order to decrease costs of electrolysis (€ net per kW) due to increased performance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fostering company- and technology competition in order to decrease costs of electrolysis (€ net per kW) due to generated scale effects	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Creation of Hydrogen Business Cases: OPEX based and CAPEX funded business cases	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Creation of Hydrogen Business Cases: Direct use of electricity for electrolysis and long term projects with low electricity prices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Creation of Hydrogen Business Cases: Additional electrolysis exemption from net fees (grid cost)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Increasing resilience of energy system by creating decentralized Green Hydrogen Economies based on Hydrogen Hubs with 10 to 15 MW (and more)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Increasing the hydrogen role in a circular economy context	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Deployment of legislation issues (including regulations, codes and standards - RCS) unified on EU level	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

C6. 4a. Please explain the missing aspect.

C7. 5. Please evaluate the following research needs in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Relevance

very high high average low very low

More fundamental research is required, e.g. research needs at low TRLs to address the present gaps. These regard new technologies based on the use of non-critical raw materials characterised by high performance, efficiency and durability.

Demonstration activities to favour the rapid creation of a distributed green hydrogen infrastructure in Europe

Addressing effective exploitation of results from research projects

.....

Companies demands (bridging industry with science); fostering technology transfer

Business cases driven R&D (OPEX based Business Cases; CAPEX will decrease later due to company- and technology competition with scale effects and increased performance

Joint research and industrial efforts on technological development of recycling of materials and components

.....

Addressing a common Terminology at EU level (e.g. JRC Report 'EU harmonised terminology for hydrogen generated by electrolysis' published - Ares(2021)4778451)

Addressing a common certification of origin to guarantee sourcing of hydrogen from green sources

Promoting programs addressing traceability, deployment mechanisms and market diffusion for green hydrogen production

Joint efforts of science, industry and active society for wide public information about the importance of hydrogen production from renewables and its utilization for fast and efficient global decarbonization

Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)

C8. 5. Please evaluate the following research needs in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Urgency

	(<3 years)short-term	(3-10 years)medium-term	(>10 years)long-term
More fundamental research is required, e.g. research needs at low TRLs to address the present gaps. These regard new technologies based on the use of non-critical raw materials characterised by high performance, efficiency and durability.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Demonstration activities to favour the rapid creation of a distributed green hydrogen infrastructure in Europe	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Addressing effective exploitation of results from research projects	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Companies demands (bridging industry with science); fostering technology transfer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Business cases driven R&D (OPEX based Business Cases; CAPEX will decrease later due to company- and technology competition with scale effects and increased performance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Joint research and industrial efforts on technological development of recycling of materials and components	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Addressing a common Terminology at EU level (e.g. JRC Report 'EU harmonised terminology for hydrogen generated by electrolysis' published - Ares(2021)4778451)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Addressing a common certification of origin to guarantee sourcing of hydrogen from green sources	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Promoting programs addressing traceability, deployment mechanisms and market diffusion for green hydrogen production	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Joint efforts of science, industry and active society for wide public information about the importance of hydrogen production from renewables and its utilization for fast and efficient global decarbonization	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

C12. 8. Please evaluate the following arguments in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Relevance

	very high	high	average	low	very low
Green Hydrogen production will strengthen the European energy security	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Green Hydrogen production could become cost competitive with natural gas at a CO2 price of 80 €/t	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Green Hydrogen production could become cost competitive with natural gas at a CO2 price of 150 €/t	<input type="checkbox"/>				
We need a strong public educational campaign introducing people to the nature, qualities and use of Green Hydrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>				
We need a clear assessment of the impact of Green Hydrogen production on water resources	<input type="checkbox"/>				
We need further studies on the safety of Green Hydrogen production	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Society in my country is generally concerned about the safety of using H2	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

C13. 8. Please evaluate the following arguments in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Urgency

	(<3 years)s hort-term	(3-10 years)medium- term	(>10 years)long- term
Green Hydrogen production will strengthen the European energy security	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Green Hydrogen production could become cost competitive with natural gas at a CO2 price of 80 €/t	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Green Hydrogen production could become cost competitive with natural gas at a CO2 price of 150 €/t	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
We need a strong public educational campaign introducing people to the nature, qualities and use of Green Hydrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
We need a clear assessment of the impact of Green Hydrogen production on water resources	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
We need further studies on the safety of Green Hydrogen production	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Society in my country is generally concerned about the safety of using H2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

C14. 8a. Please explain the missing aspect.

C15. 9. Would you like to make further comments or recommendations on the seed paper for hydrogen production?

Section D: Thematic block - Transport and Infrastructure

The seed paper on transport and infrastructure consists of three sections:

Description of status quo, target setting and needs assessment (for different countries) List of research questions Expected impacts

The complete seed paper can be downloaded [here](#) (opens in a new tab).

In the following, key aspects of the seed paper are presented in order to facilitate commenting and to achieve a targeted improvement of the document. However, it is also recommended to read the original seed paper in parallel as it contains more background information on the different aspects.

I. Country-specific strategies and conditions

II. Strategic elements of the transformation towards a hydrogen infrastructure

III. Research, development and transformation needs towards a hydrogen infrastructure

D1. 1. Please indicate your country of origin or the country about which you have transport and infrastructure-related information.

D2. 2. How would you describe the country-specific conditions for the transport of Green Hydrogen?

Are there any national plans on the development of transport infrastructure for green hydrogen?

Which strategy is followed by your country (e.g. export or import, repurposing or new build of pipelines, ship (NH₃, LOHC, LH₂), decentralised, integrated European backbone)?

Is your national infrastructure ready to absorb adequate amounts of hydrogen?

What are the main actors in the field?

Are there any national flagship projects or initiatives promoting the transport of green hydrogen?

Are there any particularities in your country that need to be taken into account for the transport of green hydrogen?

D3. 3. Please evaluate the following research questions on hydrogen production in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term). Relevance

very high high average low very low

How much hydrogen can be expected from national and European sources and what fraction has to be imported globally in the time horizons 2030, 2040 and 2050?

How should hydrogen be certified for the carbon footprint of its production process?

What is the potential for the production of low carbon hydrogen from alternative sources (pyrolysis of natural gas with CCSU, pyrolysis or plasma gasification of waste, nuclear power plants) in Europe?

Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)

D4. 3. Please evaluate the following research questions on hydrogen production in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term). Urgency

(<5 years)short-term (5-15 years)medium-term (>15 years)long-term

How much hydrogen can be expected from national and European sources and what fraction has to be imported globally in the time horizons 2030, 2040 and 2050?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
How should hydrogen be certified for the carbon footprint of its production process?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
What is the potential for the production of low carbon hydrogen from alternative sources (pyrolysis of natural gas with CCSU, pyrolysis or plasma gasification of waste, nuclear power plants) in Europe?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

D5. 3a. Please explain the missing aspect.

D6. 4. Please evaluate the following research questions on infrastructure options in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term). Relevance

very high high average low very low

Should the integration of Green Hydrogen be based on a European hydrogen backbone infrastructure from the beginning or will national hydrogen infrastructures be sufficient and more adequate for the initial period until 2030? What will be the long-term perspective for a European hydrogen backbone? How could the two systems best complement each other?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
What will be the role of container-based transport of hydrogen and hydrogen derivatives versus the transport via hydrogen pipelines in a diverse European context in the transition period until 2030 and in the long term?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
What are the most viable storage options for Green Hydrogen (physical vs. chemical)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						

D7. 4. Please evaluate the following research questions on infrastructure options in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term). Urgency

(<5 years)short-term (5-15 years)medium-term (>15 years)long-term

Should the integration of Green Hydrogen be based on a European hydrogen backbone infrastructure from the beginning or will national hydrogen infrastructures be sufficient and more adequate for the initial period until 2030? What will be the long-term perspective for a European hydrogen backbone? How could the two systems best complement each other?

.....

What will be the role of container-based transport of hydrogen and hydrogen derivatives versus the transport via hydrogen pipelines in a diverse European context in the transition period until 2030 and in the long term?

.....

What are the most viable storage options for Green Hydrogen (physical vs. chemical)?

.....

Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)

.....

D8. 4a. Please explain the missing aspect.

D9. 5. Please evaluate the following research questions on planning and regulation in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term). Relevance

very high high average low very low

Should electrolyzers be located close to the centres of renewable energy supply and storage options centrally in the grid or both rather in the vicinity of demand? Do we need a European coordination for the infrastructure planning or an integrated decision process for infrastructural development in order to integrated H2 efficiently (from technological and cost perspective) into the energy system?

.....

Should we plan infrastructures for hydrogen and electricity in an integrated framework or independently?

.....

How can the decision processes for hydrogen network planning account for the uncertain demand, production sites and import routes, while also accounting for the vital mid- and long-term role for decarbonisation?

.....

What are the requirements for institutional changes for regulating infrastructures (institutional resources, new regulatory arrangements)?

.....

What are requirements to change the commodity for existing pipelines (e.g. new approval, based on H2 concentration)?

.....

How to adapt current long-term contracts for the transmission of natural gas in case of the transformation to hydrogen transmission?

.....

How to engage with citizens to have their support for large-scale new H2 infrastructure?

.....

Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)

.....

D10. 5. Please evaluate the following research questions on planning and regulation in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term). Urgency

(<5 years)short-term (5-15 years)medium-term (>15 years)long-term

Should electrolyzers be located close to the centres of renewable energy supply and storage options centrally in the grid or both rather in the vicinity of demand? Do we need a European coordination for the infrastructure planning or an integrated decision process for infrastructural development in order to integrated H2 efficiently (from technological and cost perspective) into the energy system?

.....

Should we plan infrastructures for hydrogen and electricity in an integrated framework or independently?

.....

How can the decision processes for hydrogen network planning account for the uncertain demand, production sites and import routes, while also accounting for the vital mid- and long-term role for decarbonisation?

.....

What are the requirements for institutional changes for regulating infrastructures (institutional resources, new regulatory arrangements)?

.....

What are requirements to change the commodity for existing pipelines (e.g. new approval, based on H2 concentration)?

.....

How to adapt current long-term contracts for the transmission of natural gas in case of the transformation to hydrogen transmission?

.....

How to engage with citizens to have their support for large-scale new H2 infrastructure?

.....

Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)

.....

D11. 5a. Please explain the missing aspect.

D12. 6. Please evaluate the following research, development and transformation needs in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term). Relevance

	very high	high	average	low	very low
What is the state of H2-readiness level (i.e. 100% H2-readiness as well as readiness for H2 blending) of established technologies? What is the economic feasibility of hydrogen technologies (e.g. cost of electrolyzers) in the respective countries?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
What are the main challenges to be addressed by research, development and innovation in the field of safety of hydrogen infrastructures in particular regarding material development and sensor technologies?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
What are the main challenges to be addressed by research, development and innovation in the field of transport options based on hydrogen-derivates like ammonia and LOHC?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
What are the main challenges to be addressed by research, development and innovation in the field of liquid hydrogen transport?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
How important is the discovery of new pathways for production and use of hydrogen and how relevant is the related fundamental science?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
How could regulation, standardisation and certification of new infrastructure components and systems enable the diffusion of Green Hydrogen in Europe?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
What analytical tools and methods are needed to provide decision support for building-up a new hydrogen infrastructure?	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

D13. 6. Please evaluate the following research, development and transformation needs in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term). Urgency

(<5 years)short-term (5-15 years)medium-term (>15 years)long-term

What is the state of H2-readiness level (i.e. 100% H2-readiness as well as readiness for H2 blending) of established technologies? What is the economic feasibility of hydrogen technologies (e.g. cost of electrolysers) in the respective countries?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
What are the main challenges to be addressed by research, development and innovation in the field of safety of hydrogen infrastructures in particular regarding material development and sensor technologies?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
What are the main challenges to be addressed by research, development and innovation in the field of transport options based on hydrogen-derivates like ammonia and LOHC?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
What are the main challenges to be addressed by research, development and innovation in the field of liquid hydrogen transport?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
How important is the discovery of new pathways for production and use of hydrogen and how relevant is the related fundamental science?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
How could regulation, standardisation and certification of new infrastructure components and systems enable the diffusion of Green Hydrogen in Europe?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
What analytical tools and methods are needed to provide decision support for building-up a new hydrogen infrastructure?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

D14. 6a. Please explain the missing aspect.

D15. 7. Would you like to make further comments or recommendations on the seed paper for transport and infrastructure?

Section E: Thematic block - Market stimulation

The seed paper on market stimulation consists of six sections:

Objective and general information (scope and definitions) Description of status quo Target setting Needs assessment Questions for the public consultation Glossary

The complete seed paper can be downloaded [here](#) (opens in a new tab).

In the following, key aspects of the seed paper are presented in order to facilitate commenting and to achieve a targeted improvement of the document. However, it is also recommended to read the original seed paper in parallel as it contains more background information on the different aspects.

I. Country-specific strategies and conditions

II. Target setting and needs assessment

III. Question block: Market in general and barriers to entry

IV. Question block: System, system integration and sector coupling

V. Question block: Market support

VI. Question block: Society, public-acceptance and public-relation

VII. Question block: Internationality, cooperation and regional aspects

E1. 1. Please indicate your country of origin or the country about which you have market-related information.

E2. 2. How would you describe the country-specific market conditions for Green Hydrogen?

Are there any national plans to develop a green hydrogen market? Which strategy is followed by your country (e.g. export or import, blue hydrogen etc.)?

Are there any national regulation, funding programmes, instruments or incentives promoting the production, transport or use of green hydrogen?

Are the announced measures in your country strong enough to support fast ramp-up of a 'Green Hydrogen' economy?

What strengths and weaknesses do you see in your country in terms of a 'Green Hydrogen' economy?

E3. 3. Please evaluate the following categories of measures to promote Green Hydrogen in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Relevance

very high high average low very low

Stimulation of commercial demand: e.g. fiscal incentives, CO2-price, cross-border CO2-tax, product CO2-footprint, RE quotas, exemption from taxes and levies, emissions reduction targets, CO2 emissions standards for vehicles, RE share in aviation and maritime fuels

International agreements and multilateral cooperation: e.g. harmonised standards and trading rules, removing barriers, globally functioning system of assessing the sustainability criteria, hydrogen guarantees of origin (HGOs), multilingual permit procedures

Financing: e.g. long-term signals to foster investor confidence, mitigate salient risks, kick-start financing, grants and loans

Demonstration, communication, education: e.g. showing the important contribution to the green deal, clarify safety issues, demonstrate feasibility, create (digital) networks of experts, increase employability in the hydrogen sector through educational programmes

Regulatory framework: e.g. fasten permit procedures, regulatory framework for hydrogen infrastructure, trainings for relevant regulatory bodies

Public support: funding, providing infrastructure, consistent energy policy (focused and predictable), long-term stability, optimized transport solutions, increase GHG-emission visibility through digitalization

System analysis and assessment on a lifecycle perspective: avoid rebound effects and burden shifting, R&I activities should be pre-assessed vs. its potential to deliver net positive impacts in a full life cycle perspective

Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)

E4. 3. Please evaluate the following categories of measures to promote Green Hydrogen in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Urgency

	(<3 years)s hort-term	(3-10 years) medium-term	(>10 years)long-term
Stimulation of commercial demand: e.g. fiscal incentives, CO2-price, cross-border CO2-tax, product CO2-footprint, RE quotas, exemption from taxes and levies, emissions reduction targets, CO2 emissions standards for vehicles, RE share in aviation and maritime fuels	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
International agreements and multilateral cooperation: e.g. harmonised standards and trading rules, removing barriers, globally functioning system of assessing the sustainability criteria, hydrogen guarantees of origin (HGOs), multilingual permit procedures	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Financing: e.g. long-term signals to foster investor confidence, mitigate salient risks, kick-start financing, grants and loans	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Demonstration, communication, education: e.g. showing the important contribution to the green deal, clarify safety issues, demonstrate feasibility, create (digital) networks of experts, increase employability in the hydrogen sector through educational programmes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Regulatory framework: e.g. fasten permit procedures, regulatory framework for hydrogen infrastructure, trainings for relevant regulatory bodies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Public support: funding, providing infrastructure, consistent energy policy (focused and predictable), long-term stability, optimized transport solutions, increase GHG-emission visibility through digitalization	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
System analysis and assessment on a lifecycle perspective: avoid rebound effects and burden shifting, R&I activities should be pre-assessed vs. its potential to deliver net positive impacts in a full life cycle perspective	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

E5. 3a. Please explain the missing aspect.

E6. 4. What are the main barriers to overcome on the way to a 'Green Hydrogen' economy? Please evaluate them in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Relevance

	very high	high	average	low	very low
Price difference to fossil based energy-carriers	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Energy losses in the conversion, storage and transport of hydrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Government 'discrimination' of specific technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Lack of political courage for appropriate framework conditions	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Poor public information and therefore little public interest	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Lack/absence of a credible GO (guarantees of origin) scheme	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Inconsistent or counterproductive funding rules	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Obstructive regulatory and regional structures	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Lack of common international trade rules, harmonized regulations and standards	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Conflict of use with electrical energy	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

E7. 4. What are the main barriers to overcome on the way to a 'Green Hydrogen' economy? Please evaluate them in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Urgency

	(<3 years)short-term	(3-10 years)medium-term	(>10 years)long-term
Price difference to fossil based energy-carriers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Energy losses in the conversion, storage and transport of hydrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Government 'discrimination' of specific technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of political courage for appropriate framework conditions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Poor public information and therefore little public interest	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack/absence of a credible GO (guarantees of origin) scheme	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Inconsistent or counterproductive funding rules	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Obstructive regulatory and regional structures	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of common international trade rules, harmonized regulations and standards	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Conflict of use with electrical energy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

E8. 4a. Please explain the missing aspect.

E9. 5. How can we best create a level-playing field with fossil energy carriers? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Relevance

	very high	high	average	low	very low
No public money for fossil fuel applications	<input type="checkbox"/>				
No public money for fossil-based hydrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Increasing fossil fuel prices (CO2-pricing, ...)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Financial support for 'Green Hydrogen' and its application	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Stepwise legislation towards carbon neutrality	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Charging fossil energy carriers total costs (including external effects such as environment, health related) caused by CO2-emissions of fossil sources	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Financial support for CAPEX reduction of technology via scaling up and research	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Financial support for increase of renewable (cheap) green electricity production	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

E10. 5. How can we best create a level-playing field with fossil energy carriers? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Urgency

	(<3 years)s hort-term	(3-10 years)medium- term	(>10 years)long- term
No public money for fossil fuel applications	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
No public money for fossil-based hydrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Increasing fossil fuel prices (CO2-pricing, ...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Financial support for 'Green Hydrogen' and its application	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Stepwise legislation towards carbon neutrality	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Charging fossil energy carriers total costs (including external effects such as environment, health related) caused by CO2-emissions of fossil sources	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Financial support for CAPEX reduction of technology via scaling up and research	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Financial support for increase of renewable (cheap) green electricity production	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

E11. 5a. Please explain the missing aspect.

E12. 6. How can we best build up an open and rapidly developing ‘Green Hydrogen’ economy? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Relevance

	very high	high	average	low	very low
Cooperation beyond borders	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fast introduction of legislation towards carbon-neutrality	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Develop measures to boost renewable energy production capacities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Give easier access to research results for citizen and energy communities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Create digital networks of European stakeholders for improving knowledge-exchange and cooperation	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Strategic strengthening of ‘Green Hydrogen’ in existing or new hydrogen strategies and policies (national and European)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Creation of strategic demonstration projects and flagship initiatives	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Exchange of best practice examples	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

E13. 6. How can we best build up an open and rapidly developing ‘Green Hydrogen’ economy? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Urgency

	(<3 years)s hort-term	(3-10 years)medium- term	(>10 years)long- term
Cooperation beyond borders	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fast introduction of legislation towards carbon-neutrality	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Develop measures to boost renewable energy production capacities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Give easier access to research results for citizen and energy communities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Create digital networks of European stakeholders for improving knowledge-exchange and cooperation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Strategic strengthening of ‘Green Hydrogen’ in existing or new hydrogen strategies and policies (national and European)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Creation of strategic demonstration projects and flagship initiatives	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Exchange of best practice examples	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

E14. 6a. Please explain the missing aspect.

E15. 7. Is a bottom-up or top-down approach preferable in order to support ‘Green Hydrogen’ economy best?

- To be fair, it needs (more) top-down legislation
- The European Commission should set the legislation
- The states should set the legislation

Industry knows best what it needs to reach the goals

Other

Other

E16. 8. Which are the most important dimensions for system integration?

Infrastructure

Market design and business models

Regulation and policy

Component technologies (e.g. efficiency improvement)

Households, citizens and communities

Other

Other

E17. 9. Which are the main barriers for sector coupling?

Technology readiness level (TRL) of components

Market design

Stability of regulatory and market conditions

Resource limitations

Intransparent cost and revenue shares

Other

Other

E18. 10. Should we focus on concentrated or dispersed renewable energy production/hydrogen supply and utilization systems?

Both are necessary and should be stimulated

Both are necessary but we should focus more on dispersed energy production due to its systemic advantages

Concentrated: large units on transmission voltage levels, servicing complete electricity market system

Dispersed: smaller units on distribution voltage levels, structured into subsystems, involving direct participation of consumers and producers

Model of hydrogen supply and utilization system: Part of infrastructure – distribution networks of ‘Green Hydrogen’

Model of hydrogen supply and utilization system: Multi-energy hubs / ‘Green Hydrogen’ valleys, structured into use cases and energy eco-systems

Other

Other

E19. 11. Should development (and funding) focus on components or system-integration R&D?

- Both research areas are as important
- On components R&D
- On system-integration R&D
- Other

Other

E20. 12. How can we display GHG-emissions along the supply chain at best? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Relevance

	very high	high	average	low	very low
Mandatory life cycle assessment (LCA) for all products	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Certificates of origin for 'Green Hydrogen'	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Develop appropriate digital applications	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Label products with their GHG-emission footprint	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Label products with their environmental impact	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Introduce and display carbon-tax	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

E21. 12. How can we display GHG-emissions along the supply chain at best? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Urgency

	(<3 years)short-term	(3-10 years)medium-term	(>10 years)long-term
Mandatory life cycle assessment (LCA) for all products	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Certificates of origin for 'Green Hydrogen'	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Develop appropriate digital applications	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Label products with their GHG-emission footprint	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Label products with their environmental impact	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Introduce and display carbon-tax	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

E22. 12a. Please explain the missing aspect.

E23. 13. How can we inform people at best about ‘Green Hydrogen’? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Relevance

	very high	high	average	low	very low
Municipality workshops	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Develop easy-to-understand content	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Integrate renewable energies and hydrogen in school education	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Make potential emissions “visible” via digitalization	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Use social media to extent research’s range	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Continuous learning about ‘Green Hydrogen’ in all types of schools	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Making positive and negative environmental impacts (local resources, pollution) visible	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Making regional/local development and employment visible	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

E24. 13. How can we inform people at best about ‘Green Hydrogen’? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Urgency

	(<3 years)s hort-term	(3-10 years)medium- term	(>10 years)long- term
Municipality workshops	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Develop easy-to-understand content	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Integrate renewable energies and hydrogen in school education	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Make potential emissions “visible” via digitalization	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Use social media to extent research’s range	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Continuous learning about ‘Green Hydrogen’ in all types of schools	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Making positive and negative environmental impacts (local resources, pollution) visible	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Making regional/local development and employment visible	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

E25. 13a. Please explain the missing aspect.

E26. 14. How can we support citizen participation in ‘Green Hydrogen’ scenarios? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Relevance

	very high	high	average	low	very low
Mandatory actions forced by legislation (like vehicle exhaust emission legislation)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Roadshows	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Case-study demo approaches	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Supporting citizen energy communities	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Supporting the start-up scene and enabling people to build companies	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Allowing citizen participation in ‘Green Hydrogen’ investments	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

E27. 14. How can we support citizen participation in ‘Green Hydrogen’ scenarios? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Urgency

	(<3 years)s hort-term	(3-10 years)medium- term	(>10 years)long- term
Mandatory actions forced by legislation (like vehicle exhaust emission legislation)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Roadshows	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Case-study demo approaches	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Supporting citizen energy communities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Supporting the start-up scene and enabling people to build companies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Allowing citizen participation in ‘Green Hydrogen’ investments	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

E28. 14a. Please explain the missing aspect.

E29. 15. How can we facilitate plant permit procedures internationally better? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Relevance

	very high	high	average	low	very low
Offering multilingual permit procedures	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Deploy a European permit help desk	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Speed-up the acknowledgment of digital signatures	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Create a European legal form to support renewable energies and green hydrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Develop a platform to access needed national documentations in translation	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Permit procedures are not ta special bottleneck	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

E30. 15. How can we facilitate plant permit procedures internationally better? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Urgency

	(<3 years)s hort-term	(3-10 years)medium- term	(>10 years)long- term
Offering multilingual permit procedures	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Deploy a European permit help desk	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Speed-up the acknowledgment of digital signatures	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Create a European legal form to support renewable energies and green hydrogen	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Develop a platform to access needed national documentations in translation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Permit procedures are not ta special bottleneck	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

E31. 15a. Please explain the missing aspect.

E32. 16. How can we create internationally acknowledged vocational trainings and academic programmes to build up a hydrogen work force?

- Once, a hydrogen economy is on track, such things will develop automatically. No governmental actions are needed
- Build upon the existing partnerships of universities and create international programmes focused on renewable energies & ‘Green Hydrogen’
- Develop further training programmes for employees in the gas market
- Develop further training programmes for employees in regulatory bodies
- Engage more women in energy and transport via mentoring programmes

Other

Other

E33. 17. How can we secure a resilient international hydrogen supply? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Relevance

very high high average low very low

Develop models and continue to test them on robustness and sensitivity

Commitment to long-term hydrogen supply partnerships

Foster efficient energy use and renewable energy supply locally to simplify the additionally needed import and distribution

Decentralize the gas market to involve local communities better

Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)

E34. 17. How can we secure a resilient international hydrogen supply? Please evaluate the following aspects in terms of relevance (high to low) and urgency (short, medium, long-term).Urgency

(<3 years)s
hort-term (3-10 years
)medium-
term (>10
years)long-
term

Develop models and continue to test them on robustness and sensitivity

Commitment to long-term hydrogen supply partnerships

Foster efficient energy use and renewable energy supply locally to simplify the additionally needed import and distribution

Decentralize the gas market to involve local communities better

Other (following the evaluation of the relevance, a free text field opens for explanations)

E35. 17a. Please explain the missing aspect.

E36. 18. Would you like to make further comments or recommendations on the seed paper for market stimulation?

Section F: Your suggestions and contact details

You have reached the end of this consultation. To submit your answers, please click the *submit button* below. If you would like to make any changes, you can navigate through the consultation using the buttons at the bottom of the page. You can print out your answers on the following page.

Thank you for your participation!

F1. We welcome any further comments on the agenda process in general or on the seed papers in particular and will try to consider your feedback in the further course of implementation.

F2. Please indicate the stakeholder group to which you belong.

- Science
- Industry
- Civil society
- Public administration
- Other

Other

F3. Please let us know if we may contact you for substantive issues as we evaluate the consultation and if you would be interested in receiving information on the agenda process in the future?

- Yes
- No

F4. Please enter your contact details here.

Your personal data will be stored for a maximum of three years after the survey for the purpose of sharing information and will not be disclosed to third parties.

Name

Organisation

E-mail

Thank you for submitting your answers!

To print the completed survey, please follow the link below and choose the export option 'queXML PDF export'.

Secretariat Agenda process Green Hydrogen